

Reptiles as vectors of the spores of dictyostelids

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Abstract: Dictyostelid cellular slime molds (dictyostelids) are a group of single-celled, eukaryotic, phagotrophic bacterivores associated with the leaf litter decomposition zone of forest soils. Because the spores of dictyostelids are encased in a mucilaginous matrix, they have a limited potential for dispersal by wind. However, it has been demonstrated that animals, including some vertebrates, can serve as vectors in the dispersal of spores. This has been demonstrated for numerous birds, red-backed salamanders, and several types of small mammals, including bats. In the study reported herein, which was carried in northwest Arkansas, reptiles were assessed as possible vectors for the spores of dictyostelids, and the data obtained indicated that five of the species examined had spores present on the external surface of their bodies.

Keywords: Arkansas, cellular slime molds, dispersal, ecology, vertebrates

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Introduction

Dictyostelid cellular slime molds (dictyostelids) are single-celled, eukaryotic, phagotrophic bacterivores associated with the leaf litter decomposition zone of forest soils. Although most abundant and diverse in forest soils, these organisms also occur in other types of soils such as those of grasslands (Raper 1984, Rollins et al. 2010). In the dictyostelid life cycle, asexual spores represent the primary means of dispersal. However, unlike the spores produced by fungi and myxomycetes (plasmodial slime molds), two other groups of organisms typically found in the same type of microhabitats, the spores of dictyostelids are encased in a mucilaginous matrix and thus have a limited potential for dispersal by wind (Cavender 1973).

Relatively little published information exists on the dictyostelids of Arkansas. In what apparently represents the first report of this group of organisms from the state, Cavender and Raper (1965b) listed six species from a single locality in the western central part of the state. Later, Waddell (1982) reported eight species from Blanchard Springs Cave in northeastern Arkansas; Landolt et al. (2009) recovered 13 species during the course of a survey of 17 sites located throughout the state; and Gentry et al. (2021) isolated seven species from two types of glades in northwestern Arkansas. At the time of the present study, the total number of species known from Arkansas is 16, although Landolt et al. (2009) indicated that several of the isolates from their survey could not be assigned to any described species.

The first evidence of vertebrates serving as vectors of the spores of dictyostelids was provided by Suthers (1985), who recovered spores from fecal samples and foot swabs of seventy species of migratory

and breeding birds in overgrown fields and nearby forests in New Jersey and tropical forests in Central America. She reported that ground-feeding birds had the highest concentration of spores, whereas spores were virtually absent from strictly arboreal species. Presumably, this was because the ground-feeding species came into contact with the forest floor litter layer where dictyostelids occur. We are aware of only one other published paper on dictyostelid spore dispersal by vertebrates. In a study carried out at the Mountain Lake Biological Station in southwestern Virginia, Stephenson and Landolt (1992) recovered the spores of dictyostelids from fecal material obtained from two species of birds, five species of small mammals, and the single species of salamander they examined. Reptiles were not included in their study because it was carried out at high elevations (>1125 m) in the Appalachians where there are very few reptiles. Interestingly, Perrigo et al. (2012) investigated the occurrence of dictyostelids in samples of soil adhering to the bottoms of 18 pairs of human boots that had been used in field work and recorded four species. These authors concluded that anthropogenic dispersal of dictyostelids could play some role in the distribution patterns that have been noted for these organisms.

The objective of the study reported herein, which was carried out in northwest Arkansas, was to determine if reptiles could serve as vectors of the spores of dictyostelids. Since most reptiles come in direct contact with the forest floor litter layer when they move about, it was hypothesized that the external surface of their bodies would have an ample opportunity to pick up and then disperse spores.

Materials and methods

Reptiles examined for the presence of the spores of dictyostelids were collected in three different localities in northwest Arkansas during April 2012. Specimens were collected by hand and then released. The reptiles examined were three three-toed box turtles (*Terrapene carolina triunguis*), two western rat snakes (*Pantherophis obsoletus*), two eastern fence lizards (*Sceloporus undulatus*), one timber rattlesnake (*Crotalus horridus*), one eastern gartersnake (*Thamnophis s. sirtalis*), one little brown skink (*Scincella lateralis*), one eastern hognosed snake (*Heterodon platirhinos*), and four eastern collard lizards (*Crotaphytus collaris*). Nomenclature used for reptiles follows Trauth et al. (2004).

Figure 1. Swabbing a three-toed box turtle.

The method used for collecting the spores of dictyostelids involved dipping both ends of a standard Q-tip in a vial of distilled water, swabbing the feet, plastron (if present), and cloaca of each animal, and then placing the swab in a sterile plastic bag (Fig. 1). Individual swabs were used for each body part sampled. All swabs were taken back to the laboratory and the tip of each swab streaked across the surface of hay infusion agar in a Petri dish. Afterwards, three drops of distilled water were added to each plate to help disperse any dictyostelid spores present and the surface of the agar was inoculated with *Escherichia coli*, a standard food source for dictyostelids. The method followed represented a modification of the one described by Cavender and Raper (1965a) and used in virtually all studies of dictyostelids.

Plates were checked with the aid of a dissecting microscope, and any colonies of dictyostelids appearing were marked and then identified. Plates were maintained for several weeks. Nomenclature used for dictyostelids follows Shrikh et al. (2017).

Results

Dictyostelids appeared in plates prepared with swabs from five of the reptiles sampled. These were the three-toed box turtle, the western rat snake, the eastern fence lizard, the hog-nosed snake, and the eastern collared lizard. The species of dictyostelids recovered were *Dictyostelium mucoroides* Bref. (three isolates), *D. discoideum* Raper (two isolates), *Polysphondylium violaceum* Bref. (two isolates), and *D. sphaerocephalum* (Oudem.) Sacc. & Marchal (one isolate). Two different species of dictyostelids were recorded from three-toed box turtle and eastern fence lizard, but the total number of positive cultures was too small to determine if any ecological patterns exist with respect to habitat and/or the type of reptile from which dictyostelids were recorded.

Discussion

The species of dictyostelids recorded from reptiles are among those reported from Arkansas by Landolt et al. (2009). *Dictyostelium mucoroides*, *Polysphondylium violaceum*, and *D. sphaerocephalum* are common both in Arkansas and worldwide. This is not true for *Dictyostelium discoideum*, which has a more restricted distribution (Raper 1984). However, the species was reported previously from northwest Arkansas by Landolt et al. (2009).

The percentage of captured specimens of reptiles that were positive for dictyostelids is somewhat lower than the figure reported for small mammals and one species of salamander (the red-backed salamander [*Plethodon cinereus*]) in the study carried out by Stephenson and Landolt (1992). However, this may reflect the difference in dictyostelid spores carried externally (on the surface of the body) or internally (in fecal material). Moreover, the forests around the Mountain Lake Biological Station are moister and thus more favorable for dictyostelids than the forests of northwest Arkansas.

We are aware of only a single study that has compared the occurrence of dictyostelids both internally and externally on the same type of organism. Stephenson et al. (2007) recovered five different species from the surface of the exoskeleton of cave crickets [*Ceuthophilus gracilipes gracilipes* (Haldeman)] and a single species from fecal material. Although primarily an inhabitant of caves, this insect also can forage outside the cave. As such, its role as a vector could be to introduce dictyostelids to caves or transport spores from the forest into the cave. The occurrence of dictyostelids in caves is well-established (i.e., Landolt et al. 2006).

Active dispersal of dictyostelids by animal vectors could involve myxamoebae, microcysts, or spores (Raper 1984), but evidence suggests that spores survive passage through the digestive tract better than myxamoebae or microcysts (Suthers 1985). It seems likely that the same would apply to spores on the exterior of the body. However, this was something that could not be assessed in the present study.

In summary, although the spores of dictyostelids have a limited potential for dispersal, they can be transported by animal vectors. Among the latter, only vertebrates consistently provide the opportunity for long-distance dispersal. Birds represent the most obvious examples, but the role played by bats cannot be discounted. Bats do not ordinarily come into direct contact with the forest floor but apparently acquire dictyostelids by feeding upon insects (presumably mostly moths) that pupate in the litter layer and then emerge to carry spores aloft where they can be picked up by bats. The fact that moths can carry dictyostelids was demonstrated by Stephenson and Landolt (1992), but this aspect of dictyostelid ecology warrants additional study. The most important contribution of the present study was that it demonstrated for the first time that another group of vertebrates—reptiles—can serve as vectors of the spores of dictyostelids.

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